

The Concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* in Indian School Philosophy

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Abstract

The concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* is a fundamental aspect of Indian school philosophy. *Pramā* refers to valid knowledge, while *Pramāṇa* refers to the means or instruments through which we acquire such knowledge. Indian schools of philosophy have classified different types of *Pramāṇa*, including perception, inference, comparison, testimony, and non-perception. In Indian philosophy, *Pramāṇa* is not just limited to the physical senses, but it also includes the intellect and intuition. Moreover, each school of Indian philosophy has its own understanding of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa*, which leads to different epistemological theories and debates. The concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* has played a crucial role in the development of Indian philosophy, especially in the areas of ontology, epistemology, and metaphysics. It has also influenced Indian religious and spiritual practices, such as yoga and meditation, which emphasize the importance of direct experience and intuition as a means of acquiring valid knowledge. Overall, the concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* is a fascinating and complex aspect of Indian philosophy that continues to inspire philosophical inquiry and contemplation.

This research paper explores the concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* in Indian school philosophy. The paper examines the different types of *Pramāṇa* identified by various Indian schools of philosophy, including perception, inference, comparison, testimony, and non-perception. It also discusses how different schools of Indian philosophy understand the nature of *Pramā* and the relationship between the *Pramāṇa* and *Pramā*. The paper draws on primary sources from Indian philosophical texts to provide a comprehensive analysis of the concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa*. It also examines how this concept has influenced other areas of Indian philosophy, such as ontology, epistemology, and metaphysics. Additionally, the paper explores the practical implications of the concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* for Indian religious and spiritual practices, such as yoga and meditation. The research findings of this paper indicate that the concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* is a fundamental aspect of Indian philosophy that has played a significant role in the development of various philosophical theories and debates. Moreover, the concept has practical implications for Indian religious and spiritual practices, emphasizing the importance of direct experience and intuition as a means of acquiring valid knowledge. Overall, this research paper provides a comprehensive and insightful analysis of the concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* in Indian school philosophy.

Key words: Indian philosophy, Epistemology, *Pramā*, *Pramāṇa*, Perception, Inference, Testimony, Validity, Truth, Skepticism, *Nyāya*, *Vaiśeṣika*, *Sāṃkhya*, *Mīmāṃsā*, *Vedānta*.

Introduction

Knowledge is the arena of Indian Philosophy developed as an aid to metaphysics. It provides to method for the proper understanding of the metaphysical investigations regarding the nature of the ultimate reality and relation between the ultimate reality and the empirical self as well as the objective world. Thought every system of Indian Philosophy devotes a considerable part of discussion to the

epistemological and logical problems, yet their chief aim was to provide methodological explanation for metaphysical investigation. The sages who expound different systems of philosophy realized the nature of ultimate reality through yogic practices. They tried to convey their supernatural and mystic experiences through words of various *āgamas* precisely and methodologically. Epistemology was sought as a method for correct understanding of the metaphysical experiences handed down to us. As a result, unlike Western philosophy 'logic' could not developed as a branch of study independent of metaphysical colouring in the arena of Indian Philosophy. The study of epistemological and logical problems in Indian Philosophy under the heading '*nyāya*' which aims at discussing the process of knowing and argumentation cannot be called logic in the strict sense of the term. Logic in west is understood as formal form of argumentation but the Indian Philosophy does not demarcates formal from informal argumentation and consequently does not differentiate logic from means of knowledge. Moreover, the scope of *nyāya* is wider than that of logic; the former deals with all the means of knowledge with a metaphysical colouring whereas 'logic' is primarily concerned with inferential problems. Thus, '*nyāya*' is the study of the means of knowing and the means of testing this knowledge and does not restrict its scope only to the formal logic.

In the works on various systems of Indian Philosophy we come across minute details of various problems regarding epistemology. It is true that the discussion is the result of the extension of metaphysical problems. But still, it is also not wrong that the importance of the epistemological problems is never underestimated in the systems of Indian Philosophy. It is admitted on all hands that the true knowledge of the objects is the source and the indispensable means of the attainment of the highest end of life, liberation or *mokṣa*. Since the means of knowledge provide the path for correct understanding of the worldly objects as well as metaphysical investigations, the problems of knowledge find an important place in the systems of Indian Philosophy.

Before taking up the problem of *Upamāna* proper it will be worthwhile to discuss in brief theories of different school of Indian Philosophy regarding the valid knowledge (*pramā*) and the means of valid knowledge (*pramāṇa*).

Knowledge, in the context of philosophical investigations, may be roughly called convictions regarding reality and the means of knowledge the methods of explaining them. These convictions in general may be brought under the broad heading of *jñāna* which denotes all kinds of knowledge, true or false. When, however, man comes across various convictions regarding the same thing, he feels to verify their validity through various methods which may be roughly termed as *pramāṇas*. Perhaps, with this intention Vātsyāyana states that *Nyāya* means the examination of an object through the *pramāṇas*.¹ The basic aim of the *pramāṇas* is to test the validity of various convictions. But, the convictions which stand the test of validity are the *pramā* which denotes true or valid knowledge. Thus, *pramāṇa* in Indian Philosophy has twofold purpose of testing the validity of conviction and to rise to new valid conviction.

It is admitted on all hands that *pramā* is the true or valid knowledge. However, it begs the question regarding the test of the peculiar characteristic of validity itself. In other words, what is the factor which makes a conviction valid? This gives rise to the divergence of views regarding the mark or the true of valid knowledge and consequently the definition of *pramā* itself.

According to the Buddhists the true of knowledge consists in its practical value. They define *pramā* as the knowledge which reveals an object that is capable of successful volition,² or as the knowledge which makes us reach the object revealed by it.³ *Kamalaśīla*, however, further clarifies that the valid knowledge refers to a possible successful action; though not to the actual achievement of the object.⁴ In all these cases, it is common that the validity of knowledge depends upon the success in the practical activity.

According to the *Naiyāyikas*, the validity of knowledge consists in the objectivity or the faithfulness of the knowledge to the object. The *pramā* is generally defined by the *Naiyāyikas* as the knowledge which informs of the existence of something in a place where it actually exists. Or, in other words, *pramā* is the knowledge which predicates of something a property really possessed by it.⁵ The Prabhākara school of *Pūrvamīmāṃsā*⁶ and the *Dvaita*,⁷ the *Dvaitādvaita*⁸ and the *Śuddhādvaita*⁹ schools of *Uttaramīmāṃsā* also accept conformity of knowledge to the object as a mark of valid knowledge.

The *Viśiṣṭādvaita* school of *Uttaramīmāṃsā* holds that the validity of knowledge consists in both the faithfulness to the object and the prompting to the fruitful activity. The valid knowledge is defined there as that which apprehends an object as it really exists and which prompts fruitful activity.¹⁰

According to the *Advaita* School of *Uttaramīmāṃsā*, the validity of knowledge consists in non-contradictoriness. The followers of this school define *pramā* as the contradicted knowledge of an object.¹¹ They do not accept novelty as an essential factor for valid knowledge. That is why Dharmarāja Adhvaryu offers two definitions of *pramā* with and without novelty as a mark of *pramā*.¹²

The Bhāṭṭa School of the *Pūrvamīmāṃsā* considers the correspondence to the object, novelty and non-contradictoriness as the test of validity. Pārthasārathi Miśra defines valid knowledge as the knowledge which represents the real nature of an object, which was not attained earlier and which is not contradicted by a subletting knowledge.¹³

The *Sāṃkhya*s hold that the validity of knowledge consists in certainty (Undoubtedness), correspondence to the object and novelty as marks of the validity of knowledge. Vācaspati Miśra defines *pramā* as the *cittavṛtti* (modification of *citta*) which apprehends an object that is undoubted, real and unknown.¹⁴

The *Vaiśeṣika* consider certainty (lack of doubt), non-contradictoriness and definiteness as the marks of valid knowledge. Praśastapāda divides knowledge into *Vidyā* and *Avidyā*¹⁵ which correspond to the *pramā* (valid knowledge) and *apramā* (non-valid knowledge) respectively. Śrīdhara defines *vidyā* as firm, contradicted and definite cognition.¹⁶ Thus, the definition introduces definiteness (*Adhyavasāya*) as a mark of valid knowledge.

According to the Jaina logician's definiteness is the essential mark of valid knowledge. Vālidevasūri defines valid means of knowledge as a definite knowledge which reveals itself and the other objects.¹⁷ The Characteristic of definiteness here, however, does not differ essentially from the view of the *Naiyāyikas* because definiteness is further started by Jaina logicians themselves to be the determination of an object in the form in which it really exists.¹⁸ Siddhasena considers non-contradictoriness in place of definiteness as a mark of *pramā*.¹⁹ The definition of *Pramāṇa* offered by Akalaṅka²⁰ reveals that he considers non-contradictoriness and novelty as the marks of valid knowledge.

Thus, all the systematics unanimously holds validity or truth as the characteristic of *pramā* but differ in respect of the mark of validity or truth. The above discussion of the nature of *pramā* further reveals that according to some schools like the *Sāṃkhya* and the *Pūrvamīmāṃsā* novelty also is an essential part or differentia of valid knowledge. Some systematics like the *Vaiśeṣikas* and the Jains do not consider novelty as a mark of valid knowledge since they include remembrance (*smṛti*) into the case of valid knowledge. Some schools like the *Advaita* are indifferent to the controversy. Dharmarāja Adhvaryu defines *pramā* in two ways with and without validity as the mark of valid knowledge. Here, the crux of the problem lies in the acceptance or rejection of validity of remembrance as a means of knowledge. The *Mīmāṃsakas* and the *Sāṃkhya*s have accepted novelty as a mark of *pramā* to exclude remembrance from the domain of the valid knowledge. The Jains also accept remembrance among the forms of valid mediate knowledge. The *Advaita Vedānta* is indifferent to the problem. The *Naiyāyikas* consider the representative knowledge (*anubhūti*) as a mark of *pramā* and exclude remembrance which is not the presentation of an object but a reproduction of previous experience. The recognition of novelty as an essential factor of valid knowledge further poses the questions of the ground for inclusion of the persistent knowledge of the same object (*dhārāvāhika jñāna*) into the valid knowledge is considered as a form of valid knowledge by all systematics. The different schools assign different reasons to justify the inclusion of this kind of knowledge into valid knowledge.

As regards the nature of knowledge, there are three main theories held by different systems of Indian Philosophy. According to the *Naiyāyikas*, knowledge is an attribute of *Ātman*. The *Sāṃkhya* and *Yoga* consider knowledge to be the modification of the *buddhi*. *Buddhi* is material in nature and the supposition further leads to the conclusion that the knowledge also is material in nature. The *Buddhas* and the *Mīmāṃsakas* describe knowledge as an activity. In its most comprehensive sense the knowledge can be said to be the cognition of the objects.

The term *pramāṇa* derivatively means the extraordinary cause of valid knowledge (*pramākaraṇa*). Once attains valid knowledge of object through the means of valid knowledge. All the systems of Indian Philosophy agree in respect of literal meaning as well as the function or the purpose of *pramāṇa* that it is conducive to the valid knowledge. There is, however, divergence of opinion about the exact nature of the *karaṇa* of valid knowledge. A *karaṇa* is generally conceived as a special cause in producing a particular effect. The speciality of *karaṇa*, however, is variously interpreted by different systematics.

According to the Buddhas and the Jains, *Pramāṇa* is of the nature of knowledge. Amongst various definitions of *pramāṇa* offered by the Jain logicians it is commonly accepted that the *pramāṇa* reveals itself as well as its object.²¹ The Buddhas also define *pramāṇa* as the knowledge which is not contradicted.²²

The *Mīmāṃsakas* also hold that *pramāṇa* is the knowledge itself,²³ but they differ from the above-mentioned schools in two respects, Firstly the knowledge, according to the *Mīmāṃsakas*, unlike the Jainas, is the act or process, and secondly the result of knowledge according to the *Mīmāṃsakas*, unlike the above two schools, is distinct from the knowledge. The *Mīmāṃsakas* hold that the result of knowledge is the rise of the notion of cognisedness belonging to the object of knowledge.²⁴

The *Naiyāyikas* explain the term *karaṇa* in the sense of that which is the most conducive to the production of the effect. There is, however, difference of opinion regarding the nature of *karaṇa* between the old and new *Naiyāyikas*, which results in the divergence regarding the nature of *pramāṇa* as well. According to the old *Naiyāyikas*, the *karaṇa* is a cause which is peculiar and operative *vyāpāravadasādhāra ṇam kāraṇam*. Here, the term *asādhāraṇa* (peculiar) distinguishes *karaṇa* from other causes while the term *vyāpāravat* excludes the other objects of its genus which are not operative at the time of producing the effect but have potentiality to do so. For example, even among the causes of pot, the sticks which are not operative at the time of producing the pot are excluded from the domain of *karaṇa* by the term operative. The modern *Naiyāyikas*, on the other hand, define *karaṇa* as the cause which is invariably and immediately followed by the product (*phalāyogavyavacchinnaṃ karaṇam*). Thus, *karaṇa*, according to the ancient *Naiyāyikas* is of the nature of the substance while according to the modern *Naiyāyikas* it is of the nature of operation (*vyāpāra*) itself. For example, in case of cutting the wood with an axe the *karaṇa* according to the ancient *Naiyāyikas*, is the axe itself while according to the modern *Naiyāyikas* it is the operation of the axe. In this way, the *Karaṇa* in the case of perception, inference, *upamāna* and verbal testimony is the senses, the knowledge of probans (*liṅga*) or invariable concomitance (*vyāpti*), the knowledge of similarity and word respectively according to old *Naiyāyikas* while according to the modern *Naiyāyikas* it is the sense-object contact, consideration (*parāmarśa*), the remembrance of the statement of the reliable person and the utterance of the authoritative person respectively.²⁵

Among the *Naiyāyikas* also Jayantabhaṭṭa does not accept the normal view of his school and define *pramāṇa* as the totality of casual conditions. The *pramāṇa* according to Jayantabhaṭṭa is the totality of all the sentient and non-sentient factors which lead to the knowledge of an object which is in turn different from illusion and doubt.²⁶ Jayantabhaṭṭa is wear of the possible objections against the definition and tries to alleviate them. Firstly, the word *pramāṇa* refers to the *karaṇa*. The nature of the *karaṇa* involves the idea of its superiority over the ordinary means. Hence, it requires comparison with order means and this would not hold good if all the means are included in to *pramāṇa*.²⁷ Secondly, if the totality of casual conditions is taken to be the *pramāṇa*, it would include the object and the subject of knowledge also into the category of *pramāṇa* and such it would jeopardise the *Nyāya* position that all elements in epistemology can be finally classified into the subject, the object, the means and the process of knowledge.²⁸ Moreover, some objects which are not directly related to the process of knowing would be called *pramāṇa* but actually without the relation to the process they would not be *karaṇa* at all.²⁹ Thirdly, such a notion would go against our experience. Nothing expects the *karaṇa* is used in the third case affix. No one is found saying that perceives the object with the totality of casual conditions of perception. On the contrary, people in general are found experiencing that they know the object through their eyes or with a lamp.³⁰

Jayantabhaṭṭa alleviates all these objections thus. As to the first objection, he replies that there arises no question of comparison in the totality of causal conditions. The *kaṛaṇa* of knowledge is that the presence of which is invariably followed by the rise of knowledge. All the causes are possessed of this characteristic and, hence, there is no cause in the totality which is devoid of the nature of the means of knowledge.³¹ Replying to the second objection, Jayantabhaṭṭa says that the totality also works through the process of all the conditions included under it. Hence, the *kaṛaṇa* is not devoid of process in this case also. Moreover, the fourfold division into knower, etc., also is possible when they are invariably connected with the process of knowledge.³² As to the last objection Jayantabhaṭṭa replies that the totality is never used independent of the total members. That is why; it does not take third case affix. The usage through third affix is permitted in case of the visual organ or the lamp when the nature of producing the knowledge belonging to the totality is attributed to them. The same holds good in the case of the common experience of the usage like 'one cook with a pot' etc.³³

The *Sāṃkhya-Yoga* concept of *pramāṇa* is different from all these. *Patañjali* holds that *pramāṇais* the function of *Citta (cittavṛtti)*.³⁴ The *Yuktidipikā* states that since the *Citta* is one, the *pramāṇa* is one only.³⁵ It is through limiting adjusted that it is said to be threefold. ³⁶ *Vācaspati Mīśra* also accepts the usually accepted meaning of *pramāṇa* as the means of valid knowledge. He, however, offers two definitions of *pramā* which imply two different opinions regarding the nature of *pramāṇa* also. He defines *pramā* as the modification of *Citta (cittavṛtti)* the object of which is not doubtful (*sandigdha*), contradictory (*viparīta*) or known (*adhigata*)³⁷. The *pramāṇa* as the means of that will be sense-object contact, etc. He gives an alternate definition of *pramā* as the apprehension of the *puruṣa* which results from the modification of the *buddhi*.³⁸ In this case, the *pramāṇa* will be the modification of the *buddhi* itself. *Vijñānabhikṣu* explains it more vividly. When the result of knowledge is considered to be located in the *buddhi* the *pramāṇa* is the sense-object contact, etc., and when the result of knowledge is considered to be located in the *puruṣa* the *pramāṇa* is the function of the *buddhi* itself. ³⁹ *Vijñānabhikṣu* also makes it clear that the use of *pramāṇa* with reference to the senses is always indirect. ⁴⁰

Conclusion-

Regarding the number of the *pramāṇas* also different schools of Indian Philosophy adopted a divergent scheme. The numbers of the *pramāṇa* accepted by them differ from one to nine. The *Cārvākas* accept Perception only as a single means of knowledge. The *Vaiśeṣikas* and the Buddhists recognize two-Perception and Inference. *Sāṃkhya*, *Yoga*, and the *Viśiṣṭādvaita*, *Dvaita*, *Śuddhādvaita* and the *Dvaitādvaita* schools of *Uttaramīmāṃsā* recognise Perception, Inference and the Verbal testimony as the three means of knowledge. The *Naiyāyikas* recognize the above three with an addition of *Upamāna* as the fourth. The *Prabhākara* school *Pūrvoamīmāṃsā* and the *Advaita* School of *anupalabdhi*. The *Paurāṇikas* admit the above six with the addition of *sambhava* (inclusion), *aitihya* (tradition) and *pratibhā* (imagination). In conclusion, the concept of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* is an important aspect of Indian School Philosophy, particularly in the field of epistemology. These concepts help us understand how knowledge is acquired and what makes it valid or true. Perception, inference, and testimony are the three main sources of knowledge in Indian philosophy, and each has its own criteria for validity. The different schools of thought, such as *Nyāya*, *Vaiśeṣika*, *Sāṃkhya*, *Mīmāṃsā*, and *Vedānta*, have their own unique perspectives on *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa*. While there are some differences in their approaches, they all share the goal of understanding the nature of knowledge and how it can be acquired. Overall, the study of *Pramā* and *Pramāṇa* continues to be an important area of inquiry in Indian philosophy, providing insights into how we can acquire valid and reliable knowledge about the world around us.

Endnote -

1. *kaḥ punarayaṃ nyāya ? pramāṇairarthaparīkṣaṇam, nyāyabhāṣya* - 1.1.
2. *pramāṇamavisamvādijñānam; avisaṃvādanaśaktiniruktiḥ / arthakrayāsthitiḥ/ pramāṇavārttika* 1.2.
3. *prāpakam jñānam pramāṇam / nyāyavindutikā*, PP. 4.
4. *avisaṃvāditvaṃ cābhimatārthakrayāsamarthārthaprāpaṇaśaktikatoṣam na tu prāpaṇameva pratibandhātisambhavāt / tattoasaṃgrahapañcikā*.

5. *tadvati tatprakārahānubhavo yathārtah / saiva prametyucyate / tarkasamgrah* - P.P. 34.
6. *pramāṇamanubhūtiḥ / prakaraṇapañcikā* - PP. 124.
7. *yathārtha pramāṇam / pramāṇaprakaraṇa* - PP. 9.
8. *yathārthajñānam pramā / tadvati tatprakaratvam yathārthatoam / śrutyantakalpavalli*- PP. 91.
9. *niścayo yathārthānubhavaḥ / ayameva prameti vyavahriyate / yāthārthyam cārthānavartitoam / prasthānaratnākara*- PP. 18.
10. *yathāvasthitavyavahārānugūṇam jñānam prameti / nyāyapariśuddhi* - PP. 36. *yatīndramatadīpikā*- PP. 3 ca .
11. *pramāṇamanadhigatābādhitaviśayajñānavatvam / vedāntaparibhāṣā* - PP.19.
12. *tatra smṛtivyāvṛttam pramāṇamanadhigatābādhitaviśayajñānavatvam / smṛtisādhāraṇam toabādhitaviśayajñānavatvam / vedāntaparibhāṣā*- PP.19.
13. *kāraṇadoṣābādhakajñānarahitamagrhitagrāhijñānam pramāṇamiti / śāstradīpikā*- PP. 123.
14. *taccāsandigdḥāviparītānadhigataviśayā cittavṛttih / sāmkyatattvakaumudī*-5.
15. *samāsato dve vidye-vidyā cāvidyā ceti / praśastapādabhāṣya* - PP. 170.
16. *niḥ sandigdḥābādhitādhyavasāyātmikā pratitirovidyā, tadviparītā cāvidyāceti / nyāyakandalī* - PP. 414.
17. *svaparavyavasāyi jñānam pramāṇam / pramāṇanayatattvāloka*-1,2.
18. *vastutathābhāvagrāhakatvam niścayātmakatvena / prameyakamalamārtaṇḍa* - PP. 27.
19. *pramāṇam svaparābhāsi bādḥāvivarjitam / nyāyāvātāravārttikavṛtti* -1.2.
20. *pramāṇamavisamvādijñānamadhigatārthādḥigamalakṣaṇatvāt / aṣṭasāhāsri* - PP. 175.
21. C.F. fn. 17 and 20.
22. C.F. fn. 2and 3.
23. *agrhitagrāhi jñānam pramāṇalakṣaṇam sūcitam / śāstradīpikā*-PP.123.
24. C.F. N.M., PP. 15-16.
25. C.F. Y.V. ATHALE'S notes to Tarkas, PP. 187-9.
26. *avyabhicāriṇīmasandigdḥārthopalābdhim vidadhati bodhābodhasvabhāvā sāmagrī pramāṇam / nyāyamañjarī*- PP. - 12.
27. *kāraṇasādhano'yaṁ pramāṇam ca tamabarthaścāsayaḥ / sa cāpekṣikaḥ sāmagryāsaikatvāttadatikṛta-sādhakāntarānupalambhātkimapekṣasamyā atīśayaṁ bumaḥ / nyāyamañjarī* - PP. - 12. Vol. 1. PP. 12.
28. *evaṁ ca yaducyate pramāṇam pramāṇam prameyam pramitīti catasṛṣu vidhāsu tattoam parisamāpyate iti tad vyāhanyate / nyāyamañjarī* - PP.-12. Vol-1. PP. 12.
29. *nanu kimapekṣa sāmagyrāḥ karaṇatvamiti / nyāyamañjarī* - PP.-12. Vol-1.PP. 12.
30. *na hyeva vaktāro bhavanti laukikāḥ sāmagyrāḥ paśyāma iti tu kiṁ dīpena paśyāmaḥ cakṣuṣā nirikṣāmahe ityācaksate / nyāyamañjarī*- PP-12. Vol-1. PP. 12.
31. N.M., Part I, P. 12.
32. N.M. Part I, P. 13.
33. N.M. Part I, P. 13.
34. *pramāṇaviparyayaavikalpanidrāsmṛtayah / yogasūtrah*-16.
35. *tadekameva, buddherekatvābhyupagamāt /*
36. *upādḥivaśāntu bhinnamāśrīyate pratyakṣamanumānamityādi / yuktidīpikā* - 4.
37. *taccāsandigdḥāviparītānadhigataviśayā cittavṛttih / sāmkyatattvakaumudī*- 5.
38. *bodhaśca pauruṣeyaphalam pramā / sāmkyatattvakaumudī*- 5.
39. *atra yadi pramārūpaṁ phalaṁ puruṣaṇiṣṭhamātramucyate / tadā buddhivṛttireva pramāṇam / yadi ca buddhiniṣṭhamātramucyate / tadā tūktendriyasannikarṣādireva pramāṇam / sāmkyapravacanadhāṣya* - 1.87.
40. *cakṣurādīṣu tu pramāṇavyavahārah parampararayaiva sarvatheti bhāvah / sāmkyapravacanadhāṣya* - 1.87.

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